

Trends in Turkish port traffic by flag: Vessel arrivals and gross tonnage

Sedat Çapar^{1*}

¹ Department of Statistics, Dokuz Eylul University, Faculty of Science, Izmir, Türkiye

*Corresponding author

E-mail address: sedat.capar@deu.edu.tr

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17036908>

Received 08 July 2025

Accepted for publication 01 September 2025

Published 09 September 2025

Abstract

This study analyzes the monthly trends in vessel traffic at Turkish ports between 2015 and 2025, focusing on the distribution of Turkish and foreign-flagged ships regarding arrival counts and gross tonnage. Using aggregated port-level data, the study provides a longitudinal perspective on the structural changes in fleet composition, with particular attention to the post-2019 period. The analysis highlights consistent dominance of foreign-flagged vessels in gross tonnage and reveals a sharp decline in Turkish-flagged vessel activity after 2018, accompanied by a rise in foreign-flagged traffic. Preliminary data from early 2025 indicate a modest recovery in Turkish-flagged vessel numbers, though their tonnage contribution remains limited. These results underline the structural turning point after 2018 and the persistent dominance of foreign-flagged fleets in Turkish maritime traffic. Findings are presented through descriptive statistics and visualizations to inform future research and support operational and strategic decision-making in the maritime sector.

Keywords: vessel traffic, flag analysis, gross tonnage, Turkish ports, structural change

1. Introduction

Maritime transportation is a key driver of global trade, with over 80% of global merchandise trade by volume carried by sea (UNCTAD, 2025). Turkey is a critical node in global maritime logistics with its strategic location connecting Europe and Asia and its extensive coastline. In the last ten years, Turkish ports have witnessed notable changes in vessel traffic, which may be associated with global economic fluctuations, regional geopolitical developments, and shifts in maritime regulations. Examining the

patterns of vessel arrivals and gross tonnage is critical for assessing port capacity, guiding infrastructure planning, and informing national maritime strategy.

Understanding the dynamics of vessel arrivals and gross tonnage is essential for evaluating port capacity, infrastructure planning, and national maritime strategy. While the existing literature has explored port efficiency and freight flow optimization (Heaver, 2002; Stopford, 2013), less attention has been paid to flag-based vessel behavior and long-term structural changes in port activity.

This study investigates the monthly trends in Turkish and foreign-flagged vessel arrivals and tonnage at Turkish ports between 2015 and 2025. By employing descriptive statistics and visual analytics, the research aims to identify structural shifts in fleet composition—especially following the decline observed after 2018—and assess early signs of recovery in 2025. These findings offer valuable insights into maritime traffic composition and may serve as a reference for future operational and strategic analyses in the maritime sector.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1 Data Description

This study relies on monthly data documenting vessel arrivals at Turkish ports between January 2015 and May 2025. We categorized the data by flag state—Turkish or foreign—and included two primary variables: the number of vessel arrivals and the gross tonnage (GT) of these vessels. The data source is the national maritime statistics published by the Republic of Turkey’s Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure (Republic of Turkey, Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure, 2025).

This dataset provides a structured and time-indexed view of maritime activity, enabling short-term and long-term temporal comparisons. We created new time-based variables from the original data to facilitate temporal aggregation and enable comparison across different periods.

2.2 Methodology

This study primarily employs descriptive statistical methods and time series visualizations to examine trends in vessel traffic and gross tonnage by flag. The analysis includes monthly and annual aggregations, seasonal decomposition, and the identification of structural shifts in port activity, particularly around 2019. Key variables were grouped by flag category and plotted over time to capture differences between Turkish- and foreign-flagged vessels. Additional comparative tables were constructed to assess changes across three significant periods: 2015–2018 (pre-restructuring), 2019–2024 (post-restructuring), and early 2025 (partial recovery).

The dataset was divided into three periods based on clear structural shifts observed in the maritime sector. The pre-restructuring phase (2015–2018) represents a relatively stable period with balanced traffic between Turkish- and foreign-flagged vessels. The restructuring period (2019–2024) is characterized by a sharp decline in Turkish-flagged vessel numbers alongside the steady rise of foreign-flagged traffic. The partial recovery period (early 2025) reflects the first signs of numerical growth in Turkish-flagged vessels after several years of contraction. This classification enables a clearer understanding of structural transitions in Turkish port traffic and ensures that the analysis captures both long-term stability, periods of structural change, and the early signs of recovery.

3. Findings

3.1 Monthly Trends

This section analyzes the monthly trends in vessel traffic at Turkish ports, focusing on vessel arrivals and gross tonnage from 2015 to 2024. The analysis is disaggregated by flag state—Turkish or foreign—to capture potential differences in seasonality, structural behavior, and fleet composition. Subsections examine the total number of arrivals, the overall tonnage handled, and the average tonnage per vessel to reveal underlying dynamics in the maritime sector.

Although partial data is available for 2025, it was excluded from this section to maintain the integrity of seasonal comparisons, as only complete annual cycles were used in the time series analysis.

3.1.1 Vessel Arrivals

Figure 1 illustrates the monthly number of vessel arrivals at Turkish ports between 2015 and 2024, disaggregated by flag: Turkish-flagged and foreign-flagged vessels.

Figure 1. Monthly vessel arrivals

From 2015 through 2018, Turkish-flagged vessels frequently matched or even outnumbered foreign-flagged ones, particularly during the summer. Both groups exhibit strong seasonality, with peaks between June and October, likely reflecting heightened maritime activity due to tourism, agricultural exports, or cyclical trade demand.

A sharp and sustained decline in Turkish-flagged vessel activity began in late 2018. The sharp decline observed in 2019 and 2020 may reflect underlying structural shifts in Turkey's maritime sector, such as changes in fleet registration, new regulatory conditions, or broader economic pressures. Although signs of recovery have appeared since 2021, Turkish-flagged vessel arrivals have yet to return to their pre-2019 levels.

In contrast, foreign-flagged vessel traffic remained relatively stable throughout the observation period. Although seasonal patterns are visible among these vessels, their overall volume showed limited fluctuation, gradually making them the dominant presence in Turkish port traffic as the Turkish-flagged fleet declined.

This shift in flag-based port activity likely reflects evolving dynamics in fleet composition, policy environments, and international maritime logistics preferences.

3.1.2 Gross Tonnage

Figure 2 presents the monthly gross tonnage of Turkish- and foreign-flagged vessels arriving at Turkish ports between 2015 and 2024.

Figure 2. Monthly gross tonnage of vessels

Throughout the period, foreign-flagged vessels overwhelmingly dominated in gross tonnage. Despite Turkish-flagged vessels occasionally matching or surpassing foreign vessels in number during the early years (see Figure 1), their gross tonnage contribution remains consistently low and relatively flat. The consistently low and relatively flat gross tonnage contribution of Turkish-flagged vessels indicates that Turkish vessels are significantly smaller on average than their foreign counterparts.

Since 2015, foreign-flagged vessels have shown a steady increase in gross tonnage, with the trend becoming more pronounced after 2021. This may suggest a growing reliance on larger-capacity ships or an expansion in international port activities. The brief decline in 2020 coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic, after which the tonnage rebounded quickly and continued to rise.

Turkish-flagged vessels saw a significant drop in numbers after 2018, as illustrated in Figure 1. However, their gross tonnage did not decline proportionally, which may indicate a change in the fleet's composition. Smaller vessels were likely retired or reflagged, while larger ones continued to operate, increasing the average tonnage per Turkish vessel.

In addition, the gross tonnage time series shows slight seasonal fluctuation compared to vessel counts. Seasonal demand is managed primarily by adjusting the number of vessels, especially smaller ones, while high-tonnage operations remain relatively stable throughout the year.

This study further examines this observation in the next section, which analyzes the average gross tonnage per vessel.

3.1.3 Average Tonnage per Vessel

Figure 3 displays the monthly average gross tonnage per vessel at Turkish ports from 2015 to 2024, disaggregated by flag.

Figure 3. Average tonnage per vessel

Foreign-flagged vessels consistently exhibit much higher average tonnage than Turkish-flagged ones throughout the entire period, often exceeding 20,000 GT per vessel. This suggests that Turkey's maritime activity increasingly depends on high-capacity foreign vessels.

However, a more striking development is observed within the Turkish-flagged fleet. Although the number of Turkish vessels declined markedly around 2019, their average tonnage per vessel grew significantly in the following years. This trend suggests a structural transformation within the Turkish fleet, likely due to the retirement or reflagging of smaller vessels, leaving a core of larger, more modern ships in operation.

This pattern reinforces the earlier observation that domestic shipping capacity at Turkish ports has become more concentrated, with fewer yet larger Turkish-flagged vessels now accounting for a greater Share of activity. It also indicates a gradual move toward improved operational efficiency and competitiveness within the Turkish maritime sector.

An upward trend in foreign-flagged tonnage is also evident, although it is less striking when viewed in terms of average values. This reinforces the widening disparity in vessel size rather than in sheer numbers.

3.2 Annual Trends

This section focuses on the annual evolution of vessel traffic and tonnage at Turkish ports between 2015 and 2024. Unlike the monthly analyses in the previous section, the aim is to capture longer-term structural shifts and cumulative changes in maritime activity. The analysis is presented in three parts:

- First, Table 1 and Figure 4 highlight the total annual number of vessel arrivals, alongside year-over-year percentage changes for Turkish- and foreign-flagged vessels.
- Second, Table 2 and its corresponding figure present the annual gross tonnage, allowing for evaluation of capacity dynamics over time.

- Third, Table 3 and Figure 5 show the changing Share of gross tonnage between flag states, offering insight into evolving dominance and fleet structure.

This section analyzes absolute numbers and proportional shares to comprehensively show how flag-based maritime activity has evolved at Turkish ports over the last decade.

3.2.1 Vessel Arrivals

Table 1 and Figure 4 jointly present the annual trends in vessel arrivals at Turkish ports from 2015 to 2024. Table 1 provides year-over-year percentage changes for Turkish and foreign-flagged vessels, while Figure 4 visualizes the total annual arrivals over time by flag.

Table 1. Annual vessel arrivals and year-over-year percentage changes

Year	Turkish		Foreign	
	Total	Change (%)	Total	Change (%)
2015	38,397	-	35,288	-
2016	37,644	-2.0%	33,576	-4.9%
2017	38,263	1.6%	35,043	4.4%
2018	38,219	-0.1%	34,141	-2.6%
2019	20,991	-45.1%	34,311	0.5%
2020	15,222	-27.5%	33,599	-2.1%
2021	15,120	-0.7%	36,079	7.4%
2022	17,921	18.5%	40,131	11.2%
2023	19,277	7.6%	40,918	2.0%
2024	20,994	8.9%	39,600	-3.2%

From 2015 to 2018, Turkish-flagged vessels consistently outnumbered their foreign counterparts, maintaining annual counts around 38,000 (Table 1). This trend is visualized in Figure 4, where Turkish arrivals slightly exceed foreign ones until 2019.

Figure 4. Annual vessel arrivals

However, a sharp structural decline began in 2019, dropping Turkish arrivals by 45.1%. This was followed by an additional 27.5% decrease in 2020, reaching below 16,000. This downturn likely stems from structural changes in the domestic fleet, including vessel retirement, reflagging, or regulatory shifts.

In contrast, foreign-flagged traffic remained stable through 2019 but began to rise sharply from 2020 onward, peaking in 2023. Arrivals of foreign-flagged vessels exceeded 40,000 in 2023, marking a shift in flag dominance.

As shown in Table 1, Turkish arrivals began recovering in 2021, with growth continuing into 2024. However, levels remain below the 2015–2018 range, suggesting a partial recovery rather than a complete rebound. Meanwhile, while still dominant, foreign-flagged arrivals slightly declined in 2024, hinting at a potential stabilization in their upward trend.

These patterns reflect a significant reconfiguration in the flag composition of vessels calling at Turkish ports over the past decade. Foreign-flagged vessels have increasingly filled the gap left by the shrinking domestic fleet—especially after 2019—while Turkish-flagged arrivals, although still lagging, are beginning to show signs of gradual recovery.

3.2.2 Gross Tonnage

Table 2 and Figure 5 present the annual gross tonnage of vessels arriving at Turkish ports between 2015 and 2024, disaggregated by flag.

Table 2. Annual gross tonnage and year-over-year percentage changes

Year	Turkish		Foreign	
	Total	Change (%)	Total	Change (%)
2015	130,762,155	-	616,777,790	-
2016	142,603,067	9.1%	606,309,952	-1.7%
2017	150,243,832	5.4%	652,191,347	7.6%
2018	148,495,098	-1.2%	668,302,425	2.5%
2019	121,969,581	-17.9%	674,296,983	0.9%
2020	117,340,755	-3.8%	673,540,896	-0.1%
2021	123,686,233	5.4%	705,931,868	4.8%
2022	127,451,637	3.0%	745,877,991	5.7%
2023	127,995,058	0.4%	766,064,888	2.7%
2024	132,671,057	3.7%	769,774,171	0.5%

Figure 5. Annual Gross Tonnage

Over the past decade, foreign-flagged vessels have consistently accounted for the bulk of gross tonnage. As shown in Table 2, their annual tonnage rose from about 616 million GT in 2015 to over 769 million GT by 2024. This upward trend is also reflected in Figure 5, which illustrates a steady increase, with only a slight dip in 2020. The growth highlights the expanding presence of large international vessels in Turkish port operations.

In contrast, Turkish-flagged tonnage exhibited a less consistent pattern. Between 2015 and 2018, the tonnage increased steadily, peaking at nearly 150 million GT in 2017. However, a sharp 17.9% decline occurred in 2019, followed by an additional 3.8% drop in 2020. Although a recovery began in 2021 and continued through 2024, Turkish-flagged tonnage has not yet returned to its previous peak, stabilizing around 132 million GT.

This divergence post-2019 highlights a structural shift in the relative contributions of Turkish and foreign fleets. Between 2020 and 2024, foreign-flagged tonnage grew by more than 25% (from 673.5 million to 769.8 million GT), while Turkish-flagged tonnage increased more modestly, from 117.3 million to 132.7 million GT.

These trends reflect a widening disparity in gross tonnage capacity between domestic and international fleets. The data suggest a growing reliance on foreign-flagged vessels for maritime transport in Turkey, likely due to changes in fleet composition, port operations strategies, or broader economic dependencies.

3.2.3 Flag-Based Share in Gross Tonnage

Figure 6 and Table 3 illustrate the yearly percentage Share of gross tonnage contributed by Turkish- and foreign-flagged vessels between 2015 and 2024.

Table 3. Annual percentage Share of Turkish- and Foreign-flagged vessels

Year	Turkish Share (%)	Foreign Share (%)
2015	17.5%	82.5%
2016	19.0%	81.0%
2017	18.7%	81.3%
2018	18.2%	81.8%
2019	15.3%	84.7%
2020	14.8%	85.2%
2021	14.9%	85.1%
2022	14.6%	85.4%
2023	14.3%	85.7%
2024	14.7%	85.3%

Figure 6. Annual percentage Share of Turkish- and Foreign-flagged vessels

Throughout the observed period, foreign-flagged vessels consistently accounted for the majority of gross tonnage at Turkish ports. In 2015, Turkish-flagged vessels comprised 17.5% of the total, while foreign-flagged vessels comprised 82.5%. Although there were minor year-to-year fluctuations, this disparity remained and in some cases grew. By 2024, the Turkish Share had declined to 14.7%, with foreign-flagged vessels representing 85.3% of the total tonnage.

The most significant drop in the Turkish Share occurred in 2019, falling from 18.2% to 15.3%, which coincided with a broader decline in Turkish-flagged vessel activity. This reduction may indicate structural changes in the domestic fleet, such as reflagging or modernization strategies emphasizing operating fewer but more efficient vessels.

The sustained dominance of foreign-flagged vessels points to a broader shift in Turkey’s maritime logistics landscape, potentially influenced by global trade integration, increased chartering of foreign vessels, or domestic regulatory frameworks that may favor international operators over national ones. Similar patterns have been observed in other emerging maritime nations, where liberalization policies and cost-driven port operations have led to a decline in nationally flagged fleets (Stopford, 2013; UNCTAD, 2023).

While the Turkish fleet remains present, its diminishing proportional contribution in gross tonnage suggests a reduced role in high-volume or high-capacity shipping. This may affect national shipping policy, fleet renewal programs, and port infrastructure planning to restore or sustain domestic competitiveness in cargo throughput.

These findings underscore the need for targeted policy measures to maintain national maritime competitiveness and strategic autonomy in port logistics.

3.3 Monthly Seasonality

This section explores the seasonal patterns in maritime traffic at Turkish ports by analyzing monthly averages of vessel arrivals and gross tonnage between 2015 and 2024. Disaggregating the data by flag type—Turkish or foreign—reveals how national and international fleets respond to cyclical factors such as tourism, trade flows, and operational logistics. While previous sections focused on long-term structural

trends, the emphasis here is on intra-year fluctuations and how seasonality affects the number of vessel calls and the average cargo capacity over the calendar year.

3.3.1 Vessel Arrivals

Figure 7 illustrates the average monthly vessel arrivals at Turkish ports, categorized by flag. Both Turkish- and foreign-flagged vessels show apparent seasonal variation, with overall traffic peaking between June and October.

Figure 7. Average monthly vessel arrivals

Foreign-flagged vessels consistently outnumber Turkish-flagged ones throughout the year. However, Turkish-flagged vessel activity rises steadily from February through August, suggesting a seasonal increase potentially linked to domestic tourism, coastal trade, or national maritime operations.

In contrast, foreign-flagged vessel activity remains relatively stable across months, with only moderate fluctuations during the summer. This consistent pattern may reflect fixed international shipping routes and schedules that are less influenced by domestic seasonality.

Overall, the seasonal trend is more visible in Turkish-flagged vessels, whose operations respond more directly to mid-year economic or logistical shifts. At the same time, foreign-flagged traffic maintains a higher and steadier baseline year-round.

3.3.2 Gross Tonnage

Figure 8 displays the average monthly gross tonnage of vessels calling at Turkish ports categorized by flag. Throughout the year, foreign-flagged vessels account for the vast majority of total gross tonnage, with their monthly averages typically five to six times higher than those of Turkish-flagged vessels.

Figure 8. Average monthly gross tonnage

For Turkish-flagged vessels, gross tonnage remains relatively steady throughout the year, with only a modest increase during the summer. This suggests that while the number of Turkish ships may fluctuate seasonally, their average size shows little change over time.

By contrast, foreign-flagged vessels exhibit more pronounced monthly variation in gross tonnage. From May to October, their volumes rise slightly, peaking in October. This pattern may point to intensified use of large-capacity vessels in the year’s second half, likely tied to global trade cycles or seasonal demand.

Overall, the graph confirms that foreign-flagged vessels contribute the majority of cargo-carrying capacity in Turkish ports, in terms of volume and consistency. At the same time, Turkish-flagged tonnage is relatively modest and seasonally stable.

These findings may affect national port capacity planning, particularly in aligning domestic fleet development with seasonal high-volume periods.

3.4 Early 2025 Performance

This section focuses on the first five months of 2025 to provide an early indication of recent developments in Turkish maritime traffic. Although full-year data is not yet available, comparing January–May figures across the 2015–2025 period offers valuable insights into emerging trends. The analysis examines changes in vessel arrivals, gross tonnage, and flag-based disparities, particularly whether the modest signs of recovery observed in recent years have continued or shifted direction in 2025. By placing early 2025 data in a historical context, this section helps assess whether recent patterns represent structural changes or temporary fluctuations.

3.4.1 January–May Vessel Arrivals

Figure 9 compares the number of Turkish- and foreign-flagged vessel arrivals during the first five months (January–May) of each year between 2015 and 2025. The 2025 data—highlighted with pattern-filled bars—represent the currently available partial-year statistics.

Figure 9. Vessel arrivals between January and May

Over the past decade, Turkish-flagged vessels experienced a sharp decline in arrivals beginning in 2019, with record-low levels sustained through 2020. Since then, Turkish arrivals have shown a slow but steady recovery. In contrast, foreign-flagged vessels exhibited a consistent upward trend, especially from 2020 onward, reaching peak levels by 2023 and maintaining this momentum into 2024.

However, a notable shift is observable in 2025. Turkish-flagged vessels have increased in count compared to the same five-month period in 2024, continuing their positive trajectory. Meanwhile, foreign-flagged vessel arrivals have slightly decreased relative to the same period in the previous year. If this trend continues through the remainder of 2025, it may mark the first time in several years where Turkish-flagged traffic grows while foreign-flagged traffic contracts.

This preliminary divergence could reflect early signs of structural adjustments in the domestic maritime sector, influenced by fleet renewal, policy changes, or improved competitiveness of Turkish ports. While the changes are modest, continued observation throughout the year will be necessary to confirm whether this represents a meaningful reversal in longer-term trends.

3.4.2 January–May Gross Tonnage

Figure 10 presents the gross tonnage handled at Turkish ports during each year's January–May period from 2015 through 2025, disaggregated by vessel flag. 2025 is highlighted with a patterned fill to distinguish its provisional nature, as only partial data (first five months) are available.

Throughout the past decade, foreign-flagged vessels have consistently accounted for the majority of gross tonnage. From 2015 to 2024, this contribution showed a steady upward trend, from approximately 250 million GT in early 2015 to over 310 million GT by early 2024. Data from the first five months of 2025 continues this trajectory, surpassing 330 million GT, marking the highest early-year gross tonnage in the observed period. As (Watterson et al., 2020) observe, the expansion of open registries has led to a significant increase in foreign-flagged vessels, often at the expense of nationally flagged fleets. According to the U.S. Department of Transportation (Transportation Maritime Administration, 2011), such registries account for nearly 80% of global fleet tonnage, underscoring the scale and permanence of this structural shift.

Turkish-flagged vessels, by contrast, have shown greater variability in early-year gross tonnage. After a modest increase between 2015 and 2018, volumes declined in 2019 and 2020, likely reflecting broader structural shifts in the national fleet. Since then, the trend has gradually reversed. Preliminary data from early 2025 indicates a slight improvement over 2024, suggesting this upward trajectory may continue.

Figure 10. Gross Tonnage between January and May

While Turkish-flagged vessel arrivals saw a notable uptick in early 2025 (Figure 9), the corresponding rise in gross tonnage was comparatively modest. This suggests that although more ships are entering service, their average size remains similar to that of recent years.

Overall, the gross tonnage trends in early 2025 reaffirm the growing dominance of foreign-flagged shipping in Turkey’s maritime sector. However, the incremental rise in domestic tonnage suggests some stabilization or renewal in the Turkish fleet’s capacity. Continuous monitoring of full-year data will be necessary to determine whether this trend reflects a lasting structural shift or a temporary rebound.

These developments may signal a modest but meaningful restructuring of Turkey’s domestic shipping capabilities if sustained.

3.4.3 Flag Composition: Vessel Count vs. Tonnage Disparity

Figure 11 visualizes the flag-based composition of maritime traffic at Turkish ports during the first five months of 2025. The left panel displays the distribution of vessel count, while the right panel illustrates the corresponding distribution of gross tonnage.

Figure 11. Turkish and Foreign vessels in early 2025

The charts reveal a marked discrepancy between the numerical presence and the tonnage contribution of Turkish versus foreign-flagged vessels. Although Turkish-flagged ships accounted for 33% of total

vessel arrivals, their Share in gross tonnage was just 14.2%. In contrast, foreign-flagged vessels represented 67% of arrivals but contributed 85.8% of the total tonnage. This asymmetry reflects not only a difference in fleet scale but also in average vessel size and capacity.

This pattern is consistent with global maritime trends. Watterson et al. (2020) noted that the proliferation of open registries has encouraged shipowners to register under foreign flags for economic or regulatory advantages, often concentrating larger, high-tonnage vessels under foreign flags. The U.S. Department of Transportation (2010) also reports that foreign registries now account for approximately 80% of global gross tonnage, a structural reality that reshapes national maritime capabilities.

In the case of Turkey, 2025 data indicate that although the number of Turkish-flagged vessels appears to be recovering, their overall contribution to shipping capacity remains modest. This suggests that the current growth in the national fleet is likely driven by smaller-tonnage vessels, reflecting a revival among coastal or regional operators rather than a shift toward long-haul, high-capacity maritime trade.

These findings underscore the importance of interpreting vessel counts alongside tonnage measures, particularly in contexts where national policy goals may aim to increase domestic fleet utilization or reduce foreign dependency. Tracking these metrics will help policymakers evaluate whether such efforts result in capacity-based growth or numerical representation without scale.

3.4.5 Structural Shift and Post-2018 Recovery

Table 4 and Table 5 summarize the evolution of flag-based vessel activity at Turkish ports across three distinct periods: the pre-restructuring phase (2015–2018), the structural shift period (2019–2024), and early 2025. These segments capture key transitions in the Turkish maritime sector, particularly the sharp decline in Turkish-flagged vessel counts after 2018 and the modest signs of recovery in the most recent data.

Table 4. Comparison of Vessel Arrivals Across Three Periods

Flag	2015–2018		2019–2024		2025	
	Vessels	%	Vessels	%	Vessels	%
Turkish	14,829.50	51.7%	6,788.00	31.4%	7,819	33%
Foreign	13,867.75	48.3%	14,845.67	68.6%	15,844	67%

Table 5. Gross Tonnage Distribution by Flag Across the Same Periods

Flag	2015–2018		2019–2024		2025	
	Tonnage	%	Tonnage	%	Tonnage	%
Turkish	57,450,764	18.4%	49,641,515	14.5%	53,801,622	14.2%
Foreign	254,441,538	81.6%	291,567,772	85.5%	325,294,123	85.8%

Regarding vessel count, Turkish-flagged vessels accounted for 51.7% of total arrivals during 2015–2018. However, this Share declined sharply to 31.4% in 2019–2024, reflecting a structural downturn that began at the end of 2018. In early 2025, this figure rose to 33%, suggesting a partial reversal of that earlier decline. Conversely, foreign-flagged vessels expanded their Share from 48.3% to 68.6%, with a slight decrease to 67% in 2025 possibly indicating a stabilization in foreign dominance and the beginning of rebalancing.

Gross tonnage trends were more stable, though similarly asymmetric. Turkish-flagged tonnage declined from 18.4% in 2015–2018 to 14.5% in 2019–2024 and 14.2% in 2025. This indicates that

although more Turkish vessels returned to operation in 2025, their average size remained modest compared to their foreign counterparts. Foreign-flagged vessels continued to dominate high-capacity shipping, with their Share increasing steadily to 85.8%.

Together, these results highlight a structural transformation in Turkish maritime activity starting in 2019. While 2025 shows early signs of numerical recovery for Turkish-flagged ships, this resurgence has not yet translated into tonnage gains. This suggests that the domestic fleet's reactivation remains concentrated in smaller vessels rather than high-tonnage segments.

4. Conclusion

This study used descriptive analytics and visual exploration to examine flag-based patterns in vessel arrivals and gross tonnage at Turkish ports over the last decade. By dividing the timeline into three key periods—pre-2019 (2014–2018), post-2018 restructuring (2019–2024), and early 2025—the analysis revealed structural shifts and emerging recovery signals in Turkey's maritime sector.

One of the most significant findings was the sharp decline in Turkish-flagged vessel activity after 2018, accompanied by a concurrent rise in foreign-flagged traffic. This divergence was most pronounced between 2019 and 2022, suggesting a reconfiguration of fleet composition in favor of foreign operators. However, early 2025 data points to a partial turnaround in vessel numbers, as Turkish-flagged arrivals have increased both in absolute terms and as a Share of total traffic. Although this rise has not reached pre-2019 levels, it suggests a modest rebound in utilizing the domestic fleet.

Gross tonnage trends further highlight the disparity between Turkish and foreign-flagged vessels. Although there has been some recovery in the number of Turkish-flagged vessels, their overall contribution to gross tonnage remains relatively modest. In early 2025, foreign-flagged ships accounted for over 85% of total tonnage, underscoring a continued reliance on high-capacity foreign fleets and a limited presence of large-tonnage vessels in the domestic registry.

This study's temporal and structural patterns highlight the need for nuanced maritime policy. Simply increasing the number of Turkish-flagged vessels may not be sufficient if those vessels are disproportionately smaller and contribute little to the country's logistical capacity. Strategic investment in high-tonnage, globally competitive Turkish vessels, alongside supportive regulatory frameworks, may be required to reduce dependency on foreign fleets and restore national maritime autonomy.

Continued monitoring of post-2025 trends will be crucial to assess whether the recent uptick represents a lasting structural recovery or a temporary fluctuation. The findings presented here may also serve as a foundation for future research on the effects of flag-of-convenience policies, port infrastructure development, and the long-term competitiveness of Turkey's merchant marine.

The results of this study confirm that the post-2018 period represents a structural turning point for Turkish-flagged vessels. The sharp and sustained decline in their activity after 2018, contrasted with the steady growth of foreign-flagged tonnage, illustrates a fundamental reconfiguration of Turkey's maritime sector. Although early 2025 data suggest a modest recovery in vessel numbers, the limited contribution to overall gross tonnage highlights the continuing dependence on foreign-flagged fleets for large-capacity shipping.

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